

Transforming Trees: Combining Transformers with Boosted Decision Trees to Leverage Text Data

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Abstract

Transformers have revolutionized the field of Natural Language Processing. While transformer embeddings are extremely effective at encoding the meaning of text data, they are challenging to use as the basis of a classification task, primarily due to the high dimensionality of the embeddings, which makes traditional distance measurements, such as cosine or Euclidean, less tractable. Boosted Decision Trees, however, have been shown to excel at a wide variety of classification tasks, and have the benefit of not being reliant on geometric distance measurements. Our model combines transformer embeddings and Boosted Decision Trees in order to effectively leverage the textual data from maintenance records. Maintenance work orders in the Defense Industry can take months to complete, making accurate predictions of their eventual outcomes valuable for fleet management. The model was trained on a dataset consisting of closed maintenance records, each of which includes a description of the malfunction and the steps taken to rectify the situation. The model is shown to correctly identify the replaced components with above 90% accuracy, based on maintainer-entered text.

Key Words: Transformers, shallow learning, transfer learning, classification, clustering

1. Introduction

Large Language Models (LLMs), based on the Transformer Neural Net architecture [1], have become almost ubiquitous in their adoption for Natural Language Processing (NLP) tasks. Despite their impressive performance in NLP tasks, serious barriers exist for small teams wishing to build or fine-tune their own models. Many LLMs have been made publicly available, and by mobilizing the large amount of pretraining and knowledge present in these models small teams can gain many of the advantages afforded by LLMs without needing to build their own. In this paper we describe a combination of pretrained LLM embeddings with shallow learning techniques being applied to three distinct datasets. Combinations of this kind require minimal investment on the part of the data scientist but can produce surprisingly effective classifications or groupings in a short amount of time. In our case, this work was done as part of a prototyping process to demonstrate the power of LLMs while seeking funding for the necessary hardware in order to fine tune our own models. We will describe each of the three datasets, the combinations of LLM and shallow learning technique used, and the apparent effectiveness of each attempt. It should be noted that the abstract for this paper only mentions one dataset, but in the intervening months since the abstract was submitted we have used essentially the same technique on two new use cases. Please note that all of the data displayed in this paper is nominal, no real data from any program at Northrop Grumman Corporation is included here.

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2. Dataset One: Maintenance Records

Our team was presented with a dataset consisting of user-entered maintenance records. These records consist of some closed maintenance issues, where the repairs have been completed, and some open issues in which the repairs are ongoing. Some issues can be in an open status for months and it would be beneficial for stakeholders to be able to forecast the eventual outcome of those records once closed. In order to accomplish this task we performed simple cleaning on the text and then embedded it using the all-MiniLM-L6-v2 sentence transformer from the HuggingFace website. This is a compact version of a sentence transformer which provides several advantages in our case. First, it embeds into 384 dimensions as opposed to many other models which utilize 800 or more dimensions. This helps to alleviate the curse of dimensionality [2] [3] to some extent. Furthermore, the model is much smaller than most LLMs, allowing it to be git tracked and distributed. After embedding the text entered by the maintainers, we let all closed maintenance issues act as labeled data and trained an XGBoost classifier [4] to predict the outcome of the open maintenance issues. We performed this task on a subset of the data consisting of records pertaining to one of many systems the maintainers work on. On this subset, the classifier achieved above 92% accuracy, drastically beating a random guess which would have yielded around 8% accuracy. Further refinement and experimentation will certainly be needed when working with the full maintenance dataset, pending further investment from the customer.

3. Dataset Two: Delay Explanations

The next task undertaken by our team involved quantifying trends causing delays on a certain production task. When a delay occurs, the engineers responsible for the production line enter an explanation of the cause any delays. Management has access to all of the explanations, but it was difficult to quantify what the most consistent issues were. To address this need we embedded the text using the same sentence transformer from dataset one and then fed the embeddings into SciKit Learn's [5] K-Nearest Neighbor clustering method to group the entries. Once the entries were clustered, they became easy to label in batches. For example, in Figure 1 all of the delays were the result of waiting for QA approval, while in Figure 2 the engineers were waiting for buy off of some kind.

4. Dataset Three: Test Results

The last task involved ingesting Quality Assurance (QA) test results from another production line. The program used to track the QA test results is not well-designed, and the testers are required to enter a large amount of information in one free text entry box. As a result of this shortcoming, this data is extremely convoluted, as shown in Figure 3. This text data was also cleaned and embedded using the all-MiniLM-L6-v2 sentence transformer and then clustered using the KNN clustering algorithm. This data is so dense, however, that it remains unclear whether or not the groupings are useful. This experiment is included in this work to demonstrate that while using LLM embeddings and shallow learning is efficient and effective, it is still not universally applicable. In this instance, while this data could be cleaned with significant investment, we advised the stakeholders on this project to reassess their data collection software in order to improve its tractability with machine learning.

Unable to approve until QA review is complete
Unable to approve until QA review is complete
Unable to approve until qa review is complete.
2A: PM 05/27 Unable to approve until QA reviews.
2A: PM 05/28 Unable to approve until QA reviews.
Unable to approve until QA reviews
2A: PM 05/27 Unable to approve until QA reviews.
2A: PM 05/28 Unable to approve until QA reviews.
2A: PM 05/29 Unable to approve until QA reviews.
Unable to approve until QA review is complete

Figure 1: One example of a cluster from the delay explanation dataset. This cluster seems to exhibit a trend of waiting for QA review.

Unable to sign off materials until Buy order fulfilled
Cannot buy off on materials unti the planner buys off short lead
Waiting for Whitney to confirm before I can make my buy
Can not buyoff until tool design week 4 is bought off
Cannot buy off until BUY material orders have been bought off.
Waiting for pick order items to arrive (they are not needed yet.)
Cannot make buy off; waiting for AQI

Figure 2: Another example of a cluster from the delay explanation dataset. This cluster seems to exhibit a trend of wating for a buy or buy-off.

B979 / 5486257 / 6593842 / 5896482357

Should Be:

6895324 rev A, ACB 9, View B-B

.23" +/- .02" KSL DIA. NEAR SIDE. LOCATED AT 36.0 DEG., 122.0 DEG., 115 DEG., 169 DEG., 241 DEG., AND 259 LQD requirement.

Is:

Sink Dia at 131° measures approx. .215". Composite and Detach ring overall thickness at this location is .306". the hole diameter measures .1899".

A689 / 5864723 / 6598472 / 5869472513

Should be:

5874951 Bev Q, AQH % View A-A and Note 12.

+0.003/-0.002 Tolerance applies for a (.320) thickness. Min tolerance applies to actual size of hole (Direct measu
 (.322 dia thru hole, 152 places on the Aft attach disk).

Is:

At approximately 200°, the Aft Attach Disc hole has been countered. The depth of the counter area is .015. T

Figure 3: An example of two entries from the test results dataset. The entries were clustered together, but it is not obvious what they have in common. The data is obviously convoluted.

5. Conclusions

LLMs provide incredible leverage when working with natural language data. We have experimented with combinations of LLM embeddings and shallow-learning techniques to demonstrate that effective groupings and classifiers can be produced rapidly for prototyping and proofs of concept. These prototypes can then be followed up by more advanced machine-learning techniques, fine-tuned LLM models, and improved data cleaning and collection processes. These techniques can provide an effective on-ramp for machine learning teams looking to secure further funding for NLP-related tasks.

References

- [1] Ashish Vaswani, Noam Shazeer, Niki Parmar, Jakob Uszkoreit, Llion Jones, Aidan N. Gomez, Lukasz Kaiser, and Illia Polosukhin. Attention is all you need, 2017.
- [2] Yury Gorishniy, Ivan Rubachev, Valentin Khruikov, and Artem Babenko. Revisiting deep learning models for tabular data, 2021.
- [3] Charu C. Aggarwal, Alexander Hinneburg, and Daniel A. Keim. On the surprising behavior of distance metrics in high dimensional space. In Jan Van den Bussche and Victor Vianu, editors, Database Theory — ICDT 2001, pages 420–434, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2001. Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- [4] Tianqi Chen and Carlos Guestrin. XGBoost. In Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining. ACM, aug 2016.
- [5] F. Pedregosa, G. Varoquaux, A. Gramfort, V. Michel, B. Thirion, O. Grisel, M. Blondel, P. Prettenhofer, R. Weiss, V. Dubourg, J. Vanderplas, A. Passos, D. Cournapeau, M. Brucher, M. Perrot, and E. Duchesnay. Scikit-learn: Machine learning in Python. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 12:2825–2830, 2011.